

THE USE OF ICT IN SPEAKING CLASSES

Munavvar Bahodirovna Fazullayeva

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10279122>

Annotation. The usage of Information and communication technologies in speaking classes. The article is devoted to state about the importance of speaking fluently and accurately in foreign languages, especially in English and Russian, it is about significance and essential role of ICTs for improving English and Russian oral skill, as well as it shows technologies are as the main motivational devices for language learners.

Key words: Information and communication technology (ICT), English as a foreign language (EFL), English as a second language (ESL), Russian as a foreign language (EFL), Russian as a second language (ESL), imitative speaking, intensive speaking, responsive speaking, interactive speaking and extensive speaking, CD-ROMs and DVDs.

Аннотация. Использование информационных и коммуникационных технологий в устных курсах. В этой статье подчеркивается важность свободного владения иностранным языком, особенно английским и русским, а также роль и важность информационных и коммуникационных технологий как мотивационного инструментом для изучающих язык.

Ключевые слова: Информационных и коммуникационных технологий (ИКТ), Английский язык как иностранных языков (АИЯ), Английский второй язык, Русский язык как иностранных языков (АИЯ), Русский второй язык, имитативный речь, интенсивный речь, интеллектуальный речь, обширный речь, CD-ROM и DVD.

Annotatsiya. Informatsiya va kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining og'zaki nutq kurslarida ishlatilishi. Bu maqola hozirgi kunda chet tili ayniqsa ingliz tilida bemalol, ravon so'zlashishning qanchalik ahamiyatli ekanligi va Ingliz tilida erkin, xatolarsiz gapirishda Informatsiya va kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining o'рни, ahamiyati va muhimligi haqida bo'lib, texnologiyalarning til o'rganuvchilar uchun asosiy motivatsiya vositasi ekanligi ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Axborot va kommunikatsiya texnologiyasi (AKT), Ingliz tili xorijiy til sifatida, Ingliz tili ikkinchi til sifatida, taqlidiy nutq, intensiv nutq, idrok nutqi, interaktiv nutq, ekstensiv nutq, CD-ROM va DVD.

INTRODUCTION

It is obvious that there is great and vital role of Information and communication technologies (ICTs) in enriching English as a foreign language (EFL) learners' oral language proficiency. First and foremost we should state about speaking skill and its importance in learners' life. When thinking about learning foreign language, it should be said that the main aim of almost all learners is to be competent and fluent speakers of the target language. Most students reckon that among four main skills, speaking is the most interesting and difficult as well. However they try to pay more attention and interest to their oral performance.

We often hear and face with some learners whose English is good or bad, we may say he/she is good or bad at English. So, we should keep in our mind that it is not so easy to learn speaking English fluently and accurately when it is our second or foreign language. Many students can read and write well in the target language, but they are poor at speaking and listening. Most of learners are too afraid of talking in class. They are shy and lack confidence, even some students sound very "bookish" when they speak – it's as if they are reading from a book or it seems as they have learned by heart the context. Most learners love to speak and they are keen on speaking English, but they make many grammar and lexical mistakes. It is not surprising as English is not our mother tongue as native speaker. In order to reduce some impediments which are occurred while learning English and speaking in the target language fluently and easily we should involve the use of several simultaneous processes – cognitive, physical and socio-cultural with the help of utilizing and integrating ICTs in classroom.

According to Bygate, "speaking is a skill that all people use when they are interacting among each other; therefore, speaking is regarded as the most important skill that learners require in order to be able to speak fluently in the classroom situation" [1,4]. It is true that most language learners want to have enough practice in speaking foreign or second language in order to communicate with their peers and people who visit from overseas. It goes without saying that using a language is one of the effective ways of expressing thoughts and ideas, and opinions as well.

According to one of celebrated scholars Brown, there are five types of speaking on the basis of the speaker's intentions. They are imitative speaking, intensive speaking, responsive speaking, interactive speaking and extensive speaking [2,18].

We want to state deeply about all five types of speaking and show the importance of ICTs to improve each type.

Imitative speaking is repeating others' speech, phrase or sentence as a parrot. This kind of repetition includes itself all language features as grammar, lexis and others in order to interact in communication and in this type of speaking great attention should be paid to pronunciation. If we talk about significance of ICTs in this type of speaking there will be huge role of technologies in this part. ICT may take place of teachers in English classroom and it is used as "repetition tool" during learning new vocabularies, songs and poems and so on. It will be more useful and interesting for learners rather than the teacher's repetitions.

In **Intensive speaking** the speaker should be aware of the semantic properties of the language, as short stretches, intonation, stress and rhythm. And this type of speaking includes some assessment tasks as sentence and dialogues completion and reading aloud as well. In this part computer devices are acting as in the first type of speaking and besides that computer, projector and electronic board should be used while improving intensive speaking. In order to fulfill the tasks as dialogues, monologues, sentences completion instead of a blackboard, an electron-multimedia board can be utilized for enhancing learners' interest and motivation. As learners cannot be effective in tomorrow's world if they are trained in yesterday's skill.

Responsive speaking includes short and brief interactions as dialogues, conversations with simple questions and small talks. Such as:

A: Pardon me, do you have the time?

B: Yeah, ten fifteen.

In this kind of speaking computer tools are vital as wings of a bird. Because after watching small dialogues and conversations' videos on computer screen or projector learners may have enough practice by seeing and there will be good participation during the class. As seeing is half learning and most of students are visual type of learners, and in this case it is very handy to use IC technological devices.

Interactive Speaking differs from responsible speaking, as responsible speaking includes short conversations, however, interactive speaking involves complex and long dialogues and interactions. There are two forms of languages: transactional language and interpersonal language. The aim of transactional language is to exchange only specific information. Interpersonal language is full with slangs, ellipsis, it means it is colloquial language. Interviews, role play and

discussion activities are considered as main assessment tasks of interpersonal language. After listening or watching about some topics via projector or computer, learners may reflect their opinion on the current theme and will make discussion and debates among students.

The last type of speaking- **Extensive Speaking** includes speeches, oral presentations and story-telling. It is more formal and we cannot use informal monologues like casual speech. In order to show presentation or deliver our speech effectively we should utilize ICT technologies, it will be very fruitful and profitable for the speaker and more interesting for the audience.

There are some ICT techniques in classroom which are considered as effective and helpful for teachers to enhance learners' oral performance and they are key factors for mastering of speaking skill. Using CD-ROMs and DVDs is important in learning and teaching English. Teachers of oral expression may use these devices to teach the speaking skill for its great advantages. According to Dundey and Hockly believe that "the use of CD-ROMs in the classroom has a positive effect on students performance because when they are exposed to authentic language independently as they called autonomous learning" [3,115].

So, it is vital to utilize these tools in the teaching of speaking skill. Using DVDs is helpful for language learners as there may be given subtitles at the bottom of the video. The language learners may switch off the audio of the video and repeat subtitles several times and without subtitle they may listen and watch the video then they can act the dialogue by themselves without any subtitle or video.

Using chat is one of the essential ways of improving spoken performance, if it is well organized and well timed. Dundey and Hockly stated that "chat is a tool that allows for synchronous, real time, communication over the Internet". Chatting is considered as important tool in enriching learners' accuracy and fluency [3,71].

Speaking and writing are considered as productive and active skills while listening and reading are regarded as receptive skills. Therefore, teaching and learning one of the productive skills- speaking is more difficult rather than reading and listening. However the main aim of language study is to develop both the receptive and productive skills.

References:

1. Шомуродова Ш. Теоретические основы концептуальных метафор //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 1 (78). – С. 31-36.
2. Шомуродова Ш. Лексикографические возможности межъязыковой эквивалентности (на примере английских и узбекских фразеологизмов)

//Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2020. – №. 1 (74). – С. 70-73.

3. Шомуродова Ш. Ж. Теоретические предпосылки фразеологической деривации //Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. – 2010. – №. 22. – С. 148-150.

4. Шомуродова Ш. Ж. Теоретические предпосылки фразеологической деривации //Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. – 2010. – №. 22. – С. 148-150.

5. Абдурахимова Ф. Features of the concept of " destiny" in English and Uzbek proverbs //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 9/S. – С. 1-6.

6. Abduraximova F. SOTSIOLINGVISTIKA //Solution of social problems in management and economy. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 143-147.

7. Abduraximova F. INGLIZ, O'ZBEK VA RUS TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARNING PAREMIOLOGIK BIRLIK SIFATIDAGI O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI (PECULIARITIES OF ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN PROVERBS AS PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS) //Current approaches and new research in modern sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 77-80.

8. Abduraximova F. IMPROVING VIRTUAL EDUCATION THROUGH INNOVATIVE METHODS //Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 70-74.

9. Abduraximova F. Mentality and nationality in proverbs of English, Uzbek and Russian languages //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 691-694.

10. Джураева Ш. Г. ПОЛИФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОСТЬ АНТОНИМИЧЕСКИХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ У СУЩЕСТВИТЕЛЬНЫХ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ //УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА. – С. 47.

11. Джураева Ш. Г. ПОЛИФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОСТЬ И СЕМАНТИКА МНОГОЗНАЧНЫХ СУЩЕСТВИТЕЛЬНЫХ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ //УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА. – С. 52.

12. Джураева Ш. Г. РОЛЬ КОНТЕКСТА В РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ АНТОНИМИЧЕСКИХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ, ЗАКЛЮЧЁННЫХ В ПАРАДИГМАТИЧЕСКИХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКАХ СЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ //УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА. – С. 58.

13. Джураева Ш. Г. СООТНОШЕНИЕ СЕМАНТИЧЕСКОЙ СТРУКТУРЫ СЛОВА И ЕГО СОЧЕТАЕМОСТИ В РАЗВИТИИ ПОЛИФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОСТИ //УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА. – С. 62.

14. Исмаилов А. Вопрос формирования педагогической культуры в современной методике преподавания иностранных языков //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 2 (79). – С. 49-56.
15. Ismailov A. R. STYLISTIC AND PRAGMATIC ASPECT IN DISCOURSE ANALYSIS //Wschodnioeuropejskie Czasopismo Naukowe. – 2018. – №. 4-4. – С. 62-65.
16. Ismailov A. R. THE PROBLEM OF THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE IN MODERN METHODICS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES //Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. – 2021. – №. 4-8. – С. 46-49.
17. Ismailov A., Nasrullaev J. The use of audiovisual devices in teaching technical courses in english //Science and practice: a new level of integration in the modern world. – 2019. – С. 147-150.
18. Rustamovich D. I. A. et al. The role of verbal and non-verbal communication in learning foreign language //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 9. – С. 10-11.
19. Khamzaevna R. M. In search of a backbone mechanism in language //Евразийский научный журнал. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 8-9.
20. Rakhimova M. K. COMPARISONS AND THEIR FUNCTION IN THE NOVEL" THE GOD OF SMALL THINGS" BY A. ROY //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 708-710.
21. Bakhtiyorovna S. I., Fevzievna K. L., Khamzaevna R. M. How to support healthy class competition in an English lesson //ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 2. – С. 399-402.
22. Рахимова М. Х. и др. МАГИЧЕСКИЙ РЕАЛИЗМ В РУССКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ БУЛГАКОВА //Экономика и социум. – 2023. – №. 3-1 (106). – С. 450-454.
23. Kh R. M. «МАГИЧЕСКИЙ РЕАЛИЗМ И ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ ТРАГЕДИИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО РОМАНА А. РОЙ «БОГ МЕЛОЧЕЙ») //FINLAND" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS". – 2023. – Т. 14. – №. 1.
24. Narzikulova R. Scrutinizing materials in organizing class for high school students //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 3. – С. 31-33.

25. Narzikulova R. Peculiarities of 20th century english literature and main characteristics //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 1. – С. 247-250.
26. Narzikulova R., Ashrafi A. M. JK ROWLING'S GREAT WORKS AND THEIR SUCCESS //E-Conference Globe. – 2021. – С. 264-265.
27. Narzikulova R. A. PHONETIC ERRORS IN LEARNING ENGLISH IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2021. – №. 5. – С. 63-66.
28. Файзуллаева М. О 'tkir Hoshimov asarlarida ona obrazining lingvostilistik va lingvokognitiv tahlili //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 9/S. – С. 295-298.
29. Bahodirovna F. M. BADIY ADABIYOTDA ONA OBRAZINING YARATILISH TARIXI //FINLAND" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS". – 2023. – Т. 14. – №. 1.
30. Fayzullayeva M., Boliqulova F. O'TKIR HOSHIMOVNING" DUNYONING ISHLARI" ASARIDAGI" ONA" OBRAZINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI //Models and methods in modern science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 94-97.
31. Fayzullayeva M. B. ICT is the key of motivation in teaching FL //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 711-716.
32. Fayzullayeva M. B. THE PROBLEMS OF USAGE INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES (ICT) IN ENGLISH CLASSROOM //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 725-730.
33. Narzullayevna S. N., Odina B. Linguistic skills such as familiarity with grammatical structures, vocabulary, and phonetics //Sciencepublish. org. – С. 41.
34. Mehriniso N., Siddiqova N. N. USING INTERACTIVE METHODS FOR THE FORMATION OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES //THE THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 10-14.
35. Siddikova N. N., Gafforova S., Gafforova I. APPROACHES TO DEVELOPING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING SYSTEM IN NONLINGUISTIC HIGH SCHOOLS OF UZBEKISTAN //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 24. – С. 381-388.
36. Narzullayevna S. N., Iroda G. Types of interactive methods in developing intercultural competence in different age groups //ACADEMICIA: An

International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 4. – С. 159-162.

37. Siddikova N. N., Makhmudovna M. A., Alisherovna O. I. Philosophical and methodological analysis of organizational learning concepts //ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 2. – С. 403-407.

38. Bakhodirovna B. D. MANIFESTATION OF ARTISTIC STYLE IN CLASSICAL LITERATURE //ITALY" ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE FACE OF MODERN CHALLENGES". – 2023. – Т. 14. – №. 1.

39. Buronova D. B. Theoretical methodological basis of studying the author's art method //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 2. – С. 47-52.

40. Буронова Д. Б. MUALLIF BADIY USLUBINI O 'RGANISHNING NAZARIY METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI //МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2023. – Т. 6. – №. 1.

41. Baxodirovna, Dilnoza Buronova. "ARTISTIC STYLE OF THE WORKS OF ERNEST SETON-THOMPSON." British View 8.2 (2023).

42. Baxodirovna B. D. THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SELF STUDY IN THE CREDIT MODULAR SYSTEM ON THE EXAMPLE OF WORLD PRACTICE Eshonqulova Charos Zufar qizi //ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ИЛМИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР: ДАВРИЙ АНЖУМАНЛАР: 10-ҚИСМ. – С. 119.

